

The logo consists of the letters 'GGGP' in a bold, teal, sans-serif font. The letters are arranged in a slightly ascending sequence from left to right. A thick, teal, curved line sweeps underneath the letters, starting from the bottom left and curving upwards towards the right.

COVID-19 AND THE GGS QUESTIONNAIRE

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Content

1. Why the GGP is especially important now	1
2. Suggestion for a single question on covid-19.....	2
3. Examples from other surveys.....	3
3.1. SHARE.....	3
3.2. INTERGEN COVID	9
3.3. UNDERSTANDING AMERICA	11
3.4. GESIS PANEL.....	12

1. Why the GGP is especially important now

The COVID-19 pandemic is affecting all corners of the globe. The strict social distancing measures that have been put in place in some countries have addressed immediate health concerns but also have far reaching implications for the economy and wider society. The Generations and Gender Survey is the ideal instrument for measuring and understanding these implications. Key questions over the coming years will be the extent to which the pandemic, the measures implemented to control it, and the consequential economic crisis have affected people's family planning, job security, the quality of their relationships, the sharing of care responsibilities. Will these return to their pre-pandemic level or are they fundamentally altered in a post-pandemic world? Given the global reach of the pandemic it is also vital that these questions are answered in a coordinated and comparative way across countries, to facilitate policy learning and diffusion of best practices.

Now is the time to support and implement the Generations and Gender Survey and better understand what this new reality looks like. The Generations and Gender Survey is uniquely placed to answer these questions:

- *The Generations and Gender Programme has been collecting data for twenty years and is planning more rounds of data collection after the current one, allowing for comparisons on key measures over time.*
- *The Generations and Gender Survey is aligned with key Sustainable Development Goals and able to assess the impact of the pandemic on selected indicators.¹*
- *The Generations and Gender Survey is also global in nature with data collection planned in Europe, South East Asia, South America, North America and Australia all using the same centrally designed questionnaire.*
- *The Generations and Gender Survey is designed by leading demographers from world leading research institutes in partnership with the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe and the United Nations Population Fund.*

Key Questions the GGS will help answer:

- *Will fertility go up or down? Will this effect be long lasting or temporary? Is the impact most acute amongst the more economically vulnerable groups in society?*
- *How has access to family planning been affected? Is it harder or easier to gain access to family planning services and advice?*
- *Will social distancing measures have long term positive or negative effects on relationships? Will divorce go up or down?*

¹ Specifically, Indicator 3.7.1: Proportion of women of reproductive age (15-49 Years) who have their need for family planning satisfied with modern methods, and Indicator 5.6.1 is the proportion of women aged 15–49 years who make their own informed decisions regarding sexual relations, contraceptive use and reproductive health care.

- *Have intergenerational relationships gotten stronger during the pandemic or weakened? To what extent does this depend on the type of contact that individuals are able to have?*
- *How have reconstituted families been impacted by social distancing measures? Have ties with non-coresident parents grown weaker during social distancing measures?*

The GGS baseline questionnaire already includes a wide range of survey questions to answer the questions outlined above. In addition, countries have the opportunities to add some questions specifically on Covid-19 in the country-specific section of the questionnaire. Below are examples of single questions (composed of several items) that could be used to measure impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on several aspects of life, as well as examples drawn from other questionnaires on Covid-10 (SHARE, Intergen-COVID, Understanding America, and GESIS).

2. Suggestion for a single question on covid-19

Version A

Thinking back about the time since the beginning of the COVID-19 outbreak in [month, year]. What impact do you think the COVID-19 crisis has had on the following aspects of your life? Have they improved, worsened or stayed the same?

	<i>Improved</i>	<i>About the same</i>	<i>Worsened</i>
Your quality of life	_____	_____	_____
Your relationship with your partner	_____	_____	_____
Your relationship with person in your household	_____	_____	_____
Your relationship with family members outside your household	_____	_____	_____
Your satisfaction towards your work situation	_____	_____	_____
Your financial situation	_____	_____	_____
Your physical health	_____	_____	_____
Your mental health	_____	_____	_____

Note that this question is not very specific about the ‘timing’ of the impact: respondents might indicate that the COVID-19 crisis has negatively or positively impacted certain aspects of their life, even if at the time of the interview the situation is the same as before the outbreak. It is a very general question measuring whether the pandemic had an impact at some point in time. If one wants to know whether the respondents perceives his/her situation at the time of the interview to be different than before the start of the COVID-19 crisis, one could ask:

Version B

Comparing your current situation with your situation just before the outbreak of COVID-19 in [month, year], have the following aspects of your life improved, worsened or stayed the same?

3. Examples from other surveys

3.1. SHARE²

Corona-related infection and behavior

Now I will ask you about whether you, someone in your family or among your neighbors and friends has been affected by the Covid illness.

C02. Did you or anyone close to you experience symptoms resembling Covid (cough, fever, or difficulty breathing)?

1=yes, 2=no

IF C02=yes C03.

Who was it? Please note all persons that come to mind and their relationship to you (IWER check all that applies)

1. Respondent
2. Spouse
3. Other household member
4. Family member outside household
5. Neighbor, friend or colleague
6. Other

END IF

² http://www.share-project.org/fileadmin/pdf_questionnaire_COVID-19/SHAREw8_COVID19_qnn_20200602_routing.pdf

C04. Have you or anyone close to you been tested for the Corona virus and the result was positive, meaning that the person had the Covid disease?

1=yes, 2=no

IF C04=yes

C05. Who was tested positive? Please note all persons and their relationship to you (IWER check all that applies)

1. Respondent
2. Spouse
3. Other household member
4. Family member outside household
5. Neighbor, friend or colleague
6. Other
7. None

C06. How many persons were these together?

NUMBER

END IF

C07. Have you or anyone close to you been tested for the Corona virus and the result was negative, meaning that the person did not have the Covid disease?

1=yes, 2=no

IF C07=yes

C08. Who was tested and the result was negative? Please note all persons and their relationship to you (IWER check all that applies)

1. Respondent
2. Spouse
3. Other household member
4. Family member outside household
5. Neighbor, friend or colleague
6. Other
7. None

C09. How many persons were these together?

NUMBER

END IF

C10. Have you or anyone close to you been hospitalized due to an infection from the Corona virus?

1=yes, 2=no

IF C10=yes

C11. Who was hospitalized? Please name all persons and their relationship to you (IWER check all that applies)

1. Respondent
2. Spouse
3. Other household member
4. Parent
5. Child
6. Other family member outside household
7. Neighbor, friend or colleague
8. Other

C12. How many persons were these together?

NUMBER

END IF

C13. Has anyone close to you died due to an infection from the Corona virus?

1=yes, 2=no

IF C13=yes

C14. Who was it? Please name all persons and their relationship to you (IWER check all that applies)

1. Household member
2. Family member outside household
3. Neighbor, friend or colleague
4. Other

END IF

Emotional wellbeing

H20: So far, we talked about your physical health. Another measure of health is your emotional health or well being -- that is, how you feel about things that happen around you, and how that may have changed since the outbreak of the pandemic.

MH002. In the last month, have you been sad or depressed? If participant asks for clarification, say 'by sad or depressed, we mean miserable, in low spirits, or blue'

1. Yes
2. No

IF MH002=YES

MH002b. Has that been more so, less so or about the same as before the pandemic?

1. Less so
2. More so
3. About the same

END IF

MH007. Have you had trouble sleeping recently?

1. Yes
2. No

IF MH007=YES

MH007b. Has that been more so, less so or about the same as before the pandemic?

1. Less so
2. More so
3. About the same

END IF

MH037. How much of the time do you feel lonely?

1. Often
2. Some of the time
3. Hardly ever or never

MH037b. Has that been more so, less so or about the same as before the pandemic?

1. Less so
2. More so

3. About the same

Work

W02: Due to the Corona crisis have you become unemployed, were laid off or had to close your business?

1=Yes, 2=No

IF W02=yes

W03: How long were you unemployed, laid off or had to close your business?

NUMBER IN WEEKS

END IF

During the pandemic, some people worked at home, some at their usual work place, some both. We now ask about your situation.

W11: During the pandemic, did you work at home?

1=Yes, 2=No

W15: During the pandemic, did you work at your usual work place outside your home?

1=Yes, 2=No

IF W15 = 1 yes

W16: Did you get any protection such as masks, gloves, protective screens?

1=Yes, 2=No

W17: Did you feel safe health-wise at your work place?

1=Yes, 2=No

END IF

W20: How many hours per week did you normally work before the outbreak of the pandemic?

NUMBER

W21: Did you reduce your hours since the outbreak of the pandemic?

1=Yes, 2=No

IF W21=yes

W22: How many hours per week did you work at the peak of the crisis?

NUMBER

END IF

W23: Did you increase your hours since the outbreak of the pandemic? Please include overtime.

1=Yes, 2=No

IF W23=yes

W24: How many hours per week did you work at the peak of the crisis?

NUMBER

END IF

Economic situation

E03: Did you or any other household member receive financial support from your employer, the government, relatives, friends, and/or others since the outbreak of the pandemic?

1=Yes, 2=No

IF E03=yes

E04: Who gave you this financial support? (IWER Code all that applies)

1. Employer
2. Government
3. Relatives
3. Friends
4. Others END IF

E10: Did your ability to make ends meet worsen during the Corona crisis?

1=Yes, 2=No

IF E10=yes

E11: Did you need to postpone regular payments such as rent, mortgage and loan payments and/or utility bills?

1=Yes, 2=No

E12: Did you need to dip into your savings to cover the necessary day-to-day expenses?

1=Yes, 2=No

3.2. INTERGEN COVID³

(Intergenerational relationships and mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic, by Bruno Arpino et al.)

Mental health

C.1) During the past week, have you experienced most of the time or often any of the following items? (Tick all that apply) Please, allow the respondents to select as many options they want

- I felt that I could not shake off the blues even with help from my family or friends
- I felt depressed
- I thought my life had been a failure
- I felt fearful
- I felt lonely
- I had crying spells
- I felt sad
- I experienced some of the items above but only sometime or rarely
- I did not experience the items above at all

C.2) Compared to before the entry into force of the first nationwide restrictions due to the Coronavirus in your country (date), have you felt sad or depressed more or less than usual? (Only one option allowed) Please, allow the respondents to select ONLY ONE OPTION

- More often than usual
- About the same as usual
- Less often than usual
- I never felt sad or depressed

C.3) During the past week, have you felt lonely: (Only one option allowed) Please, allow the respondents to select ONLY ONE OPTION

- Rarely or none of the time (e.g. less than 1 day)
- Some or a little of the time (e.g. 1-2 days)
- Occasionally or a moderate amount of time (e.g. 3-4 days)
- All of the time (e.g. 5-7 days)

³ <https://www.sonar-global.eu/covid-19-projects/intergenerational-relationships-and-mental-health-during-the-covid-19-pandemic/>

C.4) Compared to before the entry into force of the first nationwide restrictions due to the Coronavirus in your country (date), have you felt lonely more or less than usual? (Only one option allowed) Please, allow the respondents to select ONLY ONE OPTION

- More often than usual
- About the same as usual
- Less often than usual
- I never felt lonely

E.1) Since the entry into force of the first nationwide restrictions due to the Coronavirus in your country (date), have you experienced any of these changes? (Tick all that apply)

Please, allow the respondents to select as many options they want

- reduction in physical activity
- worsened relation with partner
- worsened relation with other people
- suffered income loss
- lost job
- difficulties with organizing work or study from home
- death of a relative or friend due to Coronavirus
- a relative or friend was infected
- had more time to spend with family
- made new friends
- re-established a relationship with a relative or friend
- my life was not affected a big deal
- none of the above

This questionnaire also includes a very detailed section on change of contact (different types of contact) with different types of relations, using formulations like ' before/since the entry into force of the first nationwide restrictions due to the Coronavirus in your country (date), and Before/After the emergence of the first case of the Coronavirus in your country (date)

3.3. UNDERSTANDING AMERICA⁴

Childcare

[if >0 children in elementary school* with school suspended]

Are the household members in elementary school doing educational activities at home?

1. Yes
2. No
3. Other

*also asked for middle school and high school

If yes:

Who provided the educational activities?

Mark all that apply.

1. The school
2. Me or my spouse/partner
3. The child
4. Other household members
5. Other

[if any school closures] Who is mainly responsible for providing childcare while school is suspended or canceled?

Mark all that apply:

1. You
2. Your spouse or partner
3. A sibling
4. Other extended family members such as grandparents, aunts and uncles, and cousins.
5. A paid childcare provider such as a nanny or au pair
6. A childcare facility not located in your home
7. Other, please specify

⁴ <https://covid19pulse.usc.edu/>

3.4. GESIS PANEL⁵

First, the employment situation of the beginning of March is asked. Then:

For employees:

- Hat sich Ihre berufliche Situation seit der Ausbreitung des Coronavirus geändert? Sie können mehrere Antworten ankreuzen.
- Meine Stundenzahl hat sich reduziert.
- Meine Stundenzahl hat sich erhöht.
- Ich arbeite vermehrt von zu Hause.
- Ich bin freigestellt mit Lohnfortzahlung.
- Ich bin freigestellt ohne Lohnfortzahlung.
- Ich wurde entlassen.
- Nein, es hat sich nichts geändert.

For self-employed:

Hat sich Ihre berufliche Situation seit der Ausbreitung des Coronavirus geändert? Sie können mehrere Antworten ankreuzen.

- Meine durchschnittliche Arbeitszeit hat sich reduziert.
- Meine durchschnittliche Arbeitszeit hat sich erhöht.
- Ich arbeite vermehrt von zu Hause.
- Mein Umsatz ist gesunken.
- Mein Umsatz ist gestiegen.
- Ich habe mein Unternehmen aufgrund behördlicher Anordnung geschlossen.
- Ich habe mein Unternehmen freiwillig vorübergehend geschlossen.
- Die Corona-Krise bringt mich/ mein Unternehmen in finanzielle Nöte.
- Ich musste mein Unternehmen dauerhaft schließen oder Insolvenz beantragen.
- Nein, es hat sich nichts geändert

Children

Leben Kinder unter 12 Jahren in Ihrem Haushalt?

- Ja
- Nein

⁵ <https://www.gesis.org/gesis-panel/coronavirus-outbreak/longitudinal-data>

If yes ('Ja'):

Wie organisieren Sie die Betreuung des Kindes/ der Kinder während der Schließungen der Kitas, Kindergärten und Schulen? Sie können mehrere Antworten ankreuzen.

- Ich bleibe zu Hause.
- Mein Partner bleibt zu Hause.
- Die älteren Geschwister passen auf.
- Die Großeltern passen auf.
- Andere Verwandte oder Freunde passen auf.
- Ich arbeite mit Freunden/ Nachbarn zusammen, um die Kinderbetreuung zu organisieren.
- Es gibt offizielle Alternativen für meine Berufsgruppe.
- Mein Ex-Partner kümmert sich.
- Das Kind/ Die Kinder bleiben alleine zuhause.
- Sonstiges: Durch die Corona-Krise ändert sich nichts.

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